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**MODULAR LEARNING EXPERIENCES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TANGLAW
PAG-ASA RESIDENTS**

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Acceptance Page

This special/capstone project prepared by **MARIELLE O. CASTRO** with the title: **MODULAR LEARNING EXPERIENCES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TANGLAW PAG-ASA RESIDENTS** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Education Studies.

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Abstract

The Juvenile Justice Law mandates providing psychosocial and education-focused interventions to Children in conflict with the law (CICLs). The Department of Education (DepEd)'s Alternative Learning System (ALS) program, provides education opportunities to CICLs in youth rehabilitation centers for their reintegration into society. The program adopts a modular learning approach, where learners use self-learning modules (SLMs) anchored on DepEd's Most Essential Learning Competencies, or skills learners must develop to succeed academically and be job-ready. This study aimed to describe Tanglaw Pag-asa Residents' modular learning experiences. The participants are three ALS-SHS students at St. Martin de Porres Catholic School. The data was collected through semi-structured interviews and analyzed using thematic analysis. Challenges participants face include feeling overwhelmed by their workload, maintaining motivation, and lacking background knowledge of some topics. Participants are intrinsically and extrinsically motivated. They mentioned guidance from more knowledgeable others when asked how to enhance their learning experiences.

Keywords: psychosocial and education-focused interventions; children in conflict with the law; reintegration; modular learning; motivation

I. INTRODUCTION

Rationale

A study by the United Nations in 2019 found that more than one million children worldwide are in detention facilities, putting them at risk of physical, psychological, and sexual abuse. Experiences of the Philippines and other countries showed that the lack of an alternative justice system for Children In Conflict with the Law (CICL) proved harmful and ineffective in preventing them from committing similar offenses. Therefore, the country adopted such a justice system under the Juvenile Justice and Welfare Law, which focused on rehabilitation (Oco, n.d., as cited in the Juvenile Justice and Welfare Council, n.d.).

The Juvenile Justice and Welfare Law mandates establishing a justice system that recognizes and protects the rights of children at risk and in conflict with the law. Under the law, children aged 15 and below should not be held legally responsible for their actions but should undergo interventions with the help of Local Government Units (LGUs). However, those between the ages of 15 and 18, proven by the court to have committed the offense with discernment, shall undergo legal proceedings. Programs and services for these children must be child-appropriate and focused on promoting their holistic development. The law also requires the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) to establish youth rehabilitation centers in every region to cater to those who must undergo rehabilitation. While in rehabilitation centers, they are provided with educational opportunities, skills training, values formation programs, and other necessary interventions.

The Juvenile Justice and Welfare Council (JJWC) oversees the implementation of the said law, working closely with various government agencies like the DSWD and the Department of Education (DepEd) to improve the programs and services offered to children at risk and in conflict with the law.

Tanglaw Pag-asa is a youth rehabilitation center in Barangay Bulihan Malolos, Bulacan. It has 37 residents, of whom 14 are Senior High School (SHS) students, and 43 staff, including administrators, social workers, psychometricians, nurses, counsel, liaison officers, houseparents, and security guards. DepEd's Alternative Learning System (ALS) provides children and youth in special cases, including those in rehabilitation centers with learning opportunities tailored to their needs. Tanglaw Pag-asa residents can continue their studies while they undergo rehabilitation through ALS.

Modular learning is a distance learning modality that uses self-learning modules, textbooks, worksheets, and other learning resources to deliver lessons (DepEd, 2022). During the pandemic, it is one of the learning delivery modalities adopted by schools, especially in areas with limited access to technology. In this learning modality, there must be a "more knowledgeable other," often the parents or guardians, present to guide students, especially those in lower grade levels, in understanding challenging topics. According to Gunobgunob-Mirasol (2024), MKOs' role in distance learning includes assisting the child with learning activities and online learning tools.

In partnership with Tanglaw Pag-asa, St. Martin de Porres Catholic School provides self-learning modules (SLMs) for Tanglaw Pag-asa residents in Grades 11

and 12. The school's ALS-SHS teachers use DepEd's Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) as the basis for designing modules to equip them with lifelong learning skills. To monitor students' progress, the school maintains close communication with Tanglaw Pag-asa through bi-weekly consultations.

Aside from educational interventions, Tanglaw Pag-asa provides life skills interventions to its residents focused on developing greater self-awareness, practicing self-care, goal-setting, and finding purpose in life, using the toolkit developed by DSWD, JJWC, and A Child's Trust is Ours To Nurture Incorporated (ACTION Inc.). The toolkit contains modules and other reference materials that social workers and houseparents use to facilitate activities for children. Each module focuses on a specific life skill and includes activities that activate students' prior knowledge and stimulate their interest in the topic.

The study aimed to describe the experiences of CICLs at Tanglaw Pag-asa with a modular learning setup, focusing on their daily challenges, needs, and motivations. Learners' motivation can be intrinsic (driven by curiosity and desire to learn) or extrinsic (driven by rewards). Awareness of their needs and motivations is essential to make their learning experiences more meaningful and relevant.

Executive Summary

This Special Project focuses on the modular learning experiences of Grade 12 residents of Tanglaw Pag-asa Youth Rehabilitation Center in Barangay Bulihan, Malolos, Bulacan. Said institution is under the management of the Provincial Government of Bulacan, led by the Provincial Social Welfare and Development Office. Social workers at Tanglaw Pag-asa organize various activities to encourage creativity, collaboration, and reflection among residents, including but not limited to arts and crafts, reflective writing, and team-building activities. Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences states that individuals have unique abilities and interests. Providing diverse activities allows them to explore their strengths and gradually improve in certain areas.

To gain information about their study habits, daily challenges and how they deal with them, factors influencing their motivation, and suggestions to improve their learning experiences, the researcher conducted semi-structured interviews, which allows the researcher to come up with follow-up questions for participants. Interview guides and recording devices were used during the interview. Interview transcripts guided the researcher in analyzing the data. The data analysis method used was thematic analysis.

The study found that modular learning can be advantageous, as it allows for self-paced learning; however, students may require assistance from more knowledgeable others to help them succeed in such a learning setup. Self-learning modules need to be well-designed to cater to the diverse ways students learn and demonstrate their acquired knowledge and skills. The researcher also found that a supportive environment, i.e. receiving encouragement from family members, peers,

and staff, is necessary for sustained motivation. On the other hand, when they perceive a task as difficult and requires higher knowledge and skill levels, it negatively affects their motivation. Challenges they encounter on a daily basis include managing a heavy workload, lack of prior knowledge and motivation, and difficulty understanding certain parts of the module.

Through this research, I was able to affirm the importance of education research in improving teaching and learning processes to provide more meaningful learning experiences for students. I was also able to confirm that there is a need to develop a more flexible education system that caters to a wider variety of learners under various circumstances. For CICLs who are subjects of this research, education-focused interventions, alongside psychosocial support are necessary for their full participation in society.

Objectives

The lack of direct and constant supervision in modular learning poses a challenge in assessing whether Tanglaw Pag-asa residents can effectively apply their acquired knowledge and skills in answering modules. According to Atianzar (2022), the effectiveness of psychosocial and education-focused interventions relies heavily on the full cooperation of CICLs, which can only be achieved when given the motivation they need. Studies on their needs and motivations for education-focused interventions may prove useful in improving modular learning design and delivery and providing them with education tailored to their needs. This also aligns with UNICEF's recommendation to conduct studies on the learning needs of OSYs to make the ALS program more responsive to their needs and circumstances.

This research project aims to:

1. Identify the learning needs and sources of motivation for Tanglaw Pag-asa residents
2. Describe the challenges encountered by these children and how they deal with them

Significance of the study

Government agencies like DepEd and DSWD, parents of CICLs, ALS teachers, and administrators may benefit from the study. DSWD can draw on the findings and identify ways to improve interventions for CICLs. Meanwhile, this study may serve as a basis for DepEd to design learning materials anchored on the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor learning domains. The cognitive domain is concerned with developing learners' ability to recall, understand, analyze, and apply information in various situations. The affective domain deals with learners' social and emotional skills, whereas the psychomotor domain focuses on improving their motor skills, essential to completing practical hands-on activities. Parents can better support their children in their studies by knowing their needs and motivations and working closely with teachers and staff to help meet those needs. The study may also help teachers, in coordination with the staff, identify possible learning arrangements to provide more diverse learning experiences to CICLs even in a modular learning setup. Center heads may also gain insights into additional support they may provide staff to better respond to CICLs' needs.

Scope and limitation

The participants in the study are CICLs in SHS. According to DepEd (n.d.), the K to 12 Curriculum aims to hone students' knowledge and skills to enhance their preparedness for higher education and future employment, hence the need for optimal learning. The researcher excluded the length of stay at Tanglaw from the criteria, as this may vary based on social workers' assessment and recommendation (DSWD, n.d.).

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Relevant Theories

Expectancy Theory of Motivation. Vroom (1964) identified three factors influencing individuals' motivation to perform tasks: valence, instrumentality, and expectancy. Valence is the importance they give to the expected learning outcomes. Instrumentality refers to the perceived effectiveness of the methods adopted to complete tasks. Expectancy is an individual's expectation of a task's outcomes, influenced by self-efficacy and perceived difficulty (Waring, 2015). This theory can help explain respondents' motivation and willingness to participate in interventions.

Sociocultural theory. This theory states that learning and development occur and are shaped by social interactions (Vygotsky, 1978, as cited in Wang et al., 2011). A concept discussed in sociocultural theory is the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), referring to the gap between what learners can accomplish independently and with guidance from MKOs, such as their peers, teachers, and parents. The support they provide learners to help them gradually acquire skills and complete tasks unaided is called scaffolding (Belland, 2013). This theory is relevant to the present study, emphasizing the role of MKOs in teaching-learning processes. A study by Gueta and

Janer (2021) supports this theory, stating that students in a modular learning setup may benefit from the guidance of an individual with a higher knowledge level.

Visual, Auditory, Reading/ Writing, Kinesthetic (VARK) model. According to Fleming (1987), learners process information in different ways. Those with a visual learning style learn more effectively when teachers use images, videos, charts, and models to present information. Auditory learners prefer spoken information, whereas those with a reading/writing learning style find it easier to absorb text. A hands-on approach to learning works well for kinesthetic learners (Martinez and Tuesca, 2019). Fleming's VARK model provides a framework for understanding respondents' study habits.

Related Literature/Studies

Urminita-Martinez (2017) found that CICLs in the Philippines are mostly 14 to 17-year-old males in low-income populations who are unable to attend school and engage in high-risk behaviors like substance abuse. This was consistent with the study of Campoy and Campoy (2022), which revealed that delinquent behaviors were prevalent among out-of-school youth (OSYs) in Zamboanga Province.

According to UNICEF (2019), poverty and exploitation are often the main causes of juvenile delinquency, emphasizing the need to create programs and services geared toward promoting and protecting their rights. Under the Juvenile Justice Law, CICLs must have access to support services and interventions. These include but are not limited to psychosocial services, education, and skills training (Department of Social Welfare and Development, 2008).

The enactment of the ALS law, which aims to expand the ALS program's reach, marked a significant milestone in the country's education system, helping eliminate education barriers for OSYs in special cases, including CICLs. According to DepEd and UNICEF (2022), the program provided education opportunities to about 4.2 million OSYs from 2016 to 2021.

Dollison (2023) found that ALS learners are more enthusiastic about learning when they receive encouragement from their family, peers, and teachers. This was consistent with the study by Bulatao (2023), which found the importance of a strong support system in cultivating hope among CICLs. On the other hand, Caparas (2018), as cited in Mendoza et al. (2023), revealed that ALS learners' motivation is often self-driven.

Sacramento and Sacramento (2024) found a link between SHS students' motivation and the quality of SLMs. When lessons are well-structured and tailored to students' diverse learning styles, students are more eager and motivated to read and answer SLMs. Meanwhile, a study by Dotingco et al. (2021) revealed that SHS students in a modular learning setup easily become less motivated than their peers in an online setup due to the lack of direct and constant supervision from teachers.

Challenges encountered by ALS-SHS students include inadequate learning materials, lack of family and community support, and low self-efficacy (Belino and Tamangan, 2020; Tancinco et al., 2019 as cited in Mendoza et al., 2023). Meanwhile, Bustillo and Aguilos(2022) studied the challenges faced by students in modular

learning during the pandemic. They found that students struggled with understanding the content and felt overwhelmed with assigned tasks.

In a modular distance learning modality, teachers can help support and enhance student learning by providing supplementary materials like study guides and activity sheets that allow students to understand and apply concepts learned, using instant messaging applications to monitor their progress, and sustaining their motivation (Arzaga, 2023; Pangilinan, 2023; Friestad-Tate et al., 2014). These practices may enhance their learning experiences, potentially leading to better learning outcomes.

Definition of Terms

Basic learning needs. Basic learning needs are “knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes” individuals must acquire for lifelong learning and full participation in society (UNESCO et al., 1990).

Children At Risk. Children at Risk are those at high risk of committing acts punishable by law due to various factors, such as experiencing abuse, exploitation, lack of educational opportunities, and deprivation of care.

Children in Conflict with the Law. CICLs are those believed to have violated Philippine laws (The Lawphil Project - Arellano Law Foundation, Inc., n.d.).

Interventions. Fabre et al. (2016) defined interventions as a series of programs and activities to help CICLs become socially functioning individuals and prevent them from re-engaging in unlawful acts.

Learning motivation. It refers to sustained interest in achieving a specific learning goal through various intrinsic and extrinsic factors (Schunk et al., 2014). In this study, the researcher defined motivation as their level of interest and enthusiasm for learning.

Out-of-school children and youth. UNESCO Institute for Statistics (n.d.) defined out-of-school children and youth as individuals aged 6 to 14 and 15 to 24 not currently enrolled in various levels and forms of education.

Conceptual Framework

Input	Process	Output
Research participants: Tanglaw Pag-asa residents in SHS Interview guide Recording device	Data collection method: Semi-structured interviews Data analysis method: Thematic analysis	Description of the Modular Learning Experiences of CICLs at Tanglaw Pag- asa

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used qualitative descriptive design, defined by Kim et al., (2017), as cited in Doyle et al., (2020), as a research type describing a specific population, event, or situation using subjective judgments. The researcher can gain insights into the needs and motivations of Tanglaw Pag-asa residents by exploring their experiences with modular learning.

Population and Sampling

The researcher used purposive sampling to select the participants for this study. This sampling technique involves selecting participants the researcher thinks can provide rich information on the topic (Kelly, 2010, as cited in Campbell et al., 2020). Three SHS students were interviewed.

Research Instrument

The researcher developed an interview guide, outlining the questions to be covered in the interview. Using such a research instrument allows for more efficient and systematic data collection and helps the researcher keep the interview on track (Jamshed, 2014). To delve deeper into participants' experiences with modular learning, questions ranged from their daily challenges to their needs and motivations.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection method used in this study is a semi-structured interview, which allows an in-depth investigation of the research problem and is more flexible

than other interview methods (Ruslin et al., 2022). With the participants' permission, the researcher recorded the interviews.

Data Analysis Procedure

The data was analyzed using deductive thematic analysis. Braun and Clarke (2006) defined thematic analysis as a data analysis procedure where the researcher identifies patterns in a given data.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter provides a detailed account of respondents' experiences with modular learning, the challenges they face on a day-to-day basis, sources of motivation, and necessary support. The researcher conducted a thematic analysis and identified five themes: increased autonomy, academic challenges, extrinsic and intrinsic sources of motivation, more diverse activities, and scaffolding.

Results

Increased autonomy:

One advantage of modular learning for respondents is that it allows them to learn at their own pace. In such a learning setup, they plan and manage their own schedule so they can allot more time on challenging topics, especially those they have not encountered before. They also choose which resources to use, alongside self-learning modules, to improve their understanding of concepts. Respondents with verbal learning styles often read books in Math, Science, and other subjects and use them as references when answering modules.

Academic challenges:

The challenges they encounter include managing a heavy workload, maintaining a high level of motivation, and understanding the content. Students have three months to complete the assigned modules. Despite their desire and enthusiasm for learning, respondents disclosed instances when they felt overwhelmed by the number of modules they must finish, which negatively affected their motivation. The absence of direct instruction and supervision in modular learning poses a challenge to respondents given their lack of background knowledge in some of the lessons included in the curriculum. One respondent noted difficulty in achieving expected learning outcomes, recalling instances when he did not fully understand what was written in the module.

“Minsan nakakasagot ako sa module ko pero yung iba, hindi ko naman po natututunan talaga.”

Motivational factors:

Respondents cited parental support, recognition of their hard work and accomplishments, and desire to learn when asked what motivates them. Despite facing various challenges, they remain determined and eager to finish their studies to build a better future for themselves and their families. Being praised for their hard work increases their motivation to learn. One respondent said receiving positive feedback gives him a sense of fulfillment and motivation.

“Mas nakakagana rin po mag-aral kapag pinupuri ka, sasabihin na “Ang galing mo, ipagpatuloy mo ‘yan.” Masarap sa pakiramdam na may mga tao pa lang natutuwa

sa iyo, nakikita yung mga ginagawa mo. Kahit na nandito ka, maipagmamalaki ka nila dahil sa ginagawa mo.”

Respondents left school and worked at an early age to help support their families before becoming residents of Tanglaw Pag-asa. This fuels their desire and willingness to learn and make the most of the opportunity to continue their studies.

“Nito kasing nakaraang taon, halos ako yung naghihintay sa module talaga. Kasi nga, dito lang ulit ako nakapagsimula mag-aral. Nabigyan ako ng pagkakataong mag-aral dito kaya excited ako.”

On the other hand, low self-efficacy and perceived difficulty of tasks were identified as factors negatively affecting their motivation. This is mostly true when answering Mathematics-related learning activities.

Diversify activities and provide scaffolding:

Respondents find it important to have an MKO present who can provide them with instruction and feedback just like in a face-to-face learning setup. They also mentioned the diversity of activities students could do in in-person classes to improve their written and verbal communication skills.

“Gusto namin mag present, hindi namin magawa kasi modular lang kami. Gusto namin magbahagi ng nalalaman namin kasi sa face-to-face ganoon, papatayuin ka sa harap, magpapaliwanag ka, at magpe-present ka pero sa modular wala.”

“Kapag face-to-face kasi, sobrang daming tinuturo, nagsusulat ka, [at] mas maraming activities. Hindi po kagaya sa modular, sasagutan mo lang sa papel. Sa face-to-face, isusulat mo pa, talagang mahahasa ka sa pag-aaral, mahahasa ka magsulat [at] magbasa.”

Discussion

Using Fleming’s VARK model, the participants in the study were classified as auditory and verbal learners. The former learns more effectively by listening to information, whereas the latter finds it easier to absorb written information. Respondents use books and online learning materials respectively to supplement SLMs.

The results indicate that modular learning has advantages and disadvantages as with other learning modalities. As cited in Dejene and Chen (2019), it allows learners greater control over their learning; however, such a learning setup proves challenging without sufficient prior knowledge of the topics and interactions with teachers. Consistent with Vygotsky’s Sociocultural theory, respondents recognize the importance of MKOs in providing instruction and guidance to learners, especially with unfamiliar topics or tasks they have not fully mastered. As previously stated, the MKO can be an adult or someone their age with a higher knowledge level who can help them achieve the expected learning outcomes. MKOs help learners by breaking tasks into manageable parts and demonstrating various problem-solving methods (Gauvain, 2020). For Tanglaw Pag-asa residents, scaffolding may involve guiding them through complex Mathematical problems, as respondents reported struggling with advanced Math.

As to motivation, the researcher found an interplay of intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Consistent with Dollison's (2023) and Bulatao's (2023) studies, supportive family members, staff, and peers positively affect respondents' motivation. Meanwhile, intrinsic factors, specifically a sense of fulfillment and satisfaction in learning, are also at play, similar to the study by Caparas (2018).

The findings also support the Expectancy theory, which states that the effort exerted on a task depends on the perceived outcomes. Respondents give importance to completing their studies and having the capacity to help support their families, hence they exert more effort in their studies. They strive to complete and submit their modules on time.

In contrast to Belino and Tamangan (2020), ALS-SHS students at Tanglaw Pag-asa receive adequate support from their immediate surroundings, including family, staff, and peers. However, low self-efficacy, consistent with the study of Tancinco et al. (2019) and the Expectancy theory, leads to low motivation among respondents.

In line with the study by Sacramento and Sacramento (2024), the study found that when designing self-learning modules, one must consider the diverse ways students learn and demonstrate the knowledge and skills they acquired. For respondents, objective-type activities, which mainly assess students' ability to recall facts, do not fully capture learning. The Universal Design for Learning, which focuses on tailoring education to students' diverse needs to make it more accessible, relevant,

and engaging (Dalton et al., 2019, as cited in Wells, 2022), emphasizes allowing students to apply what they learn in multiple and varied ways.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary and Conclusions

Education allows individuals to reach their full potential and contribute positively to society. Providing alternative learning opportunities for those unable to receive formal instruction strengthens efforts to ensure equal access to quality education. Education-focused interventions help CICLs acquire knowledge and skills to improve their quality of life in the long run. This study described the modular learning experiences of Tanglaw Pag-asa residents in Grades 11 and 12, providing insights into how education can be made more accessible and responsive to their needs. Modular learning proved beneficial to children in conflict with the law; it goes hand in hand with psychosocial interventions to help them develop into well-rounded individuals. However, it can be challenging without adequate support, guidance, and motivation to learn like other distance learning modalities. To create effective learning experiences for children in conflict with the law, one must be fully aware of and understand how they learn best and what motivates them.

Recommendations

Television-based instruction may help enhance the teaching-learning process as this instructional method uses several media to deliver instruction to students. Mayer's Multimedia Learning Theory states that using multiple media such as text and images allows students to process information more easily than using only one

medium (Mayer, 1997, as cited in Yana, n.d.). In the case of Tanglaw Pag-asa, educational programs may supplement the self-learning modules created by DepEd and teachers. Combining the two learning modalities may benefit students with visual, auditory, and verbal-linguistic learning styles. Integrating hands-on activities is also essential, especially for kinesthetic learners. However, they may need to be supervised by Tanglaw Pag-asa staff.

Future researchers may build on the study and explore other factors shaping CICLs' modular learning experiences, such as their perceptions and readiness for self-paced learning, level of parental involvement, and past learning experiences. Guzman and Guitering-Mansibang (2022) found that when learners are unprepared to engage in a new learning modality, it may lead to poor learning outcomes.

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APPENDICES
APPENDIX A

Approval letter

PROVINCIAL SOCIAL WELFARE AND DEVELOPMENT OFFICE

June 04, 2024

MS. MARIEL O. CASTRO

Student

University of the Philippines Open University

Dear **Ms. Castro**:

Greetings!

This in reference to your request to conduct a research study at Tanglaw Pag-asa Youth Rehabilitation Center. We would like to inform you that your request has been approved.

For additional information or if you have any queries you may contact us at (044) 802-7343 or email us at tpyrcbulacan@gmail.com.

Thank you very much.

Sincerely,

JAY MARK P. CHICO, RSW, MPA, MABS
PG-ADH, PSWDO Center Head, TPYRC

G/F Capitol Bldg., Antonio S. Bautista Bulacan Provincial
Capital Compound, City of Malolos, Bulacan 3000
Tel: +(63)44 791-8133 Email: pswdo@bulacan.gov.ph

GOV. DANIEL R. FERNANDO
VICE GOV. ALEX C. CASTRO
AND SANGUNIANG PANGALAWIGAN

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APPENDIX B

Gatekeeper/ External Adviser's Approval

Special Project in Bachelor of Education Studies

The first page of the consent form is to be accomplished by the students in the Bachelor of Education Studies (BES) program at the University of the Philippines Open University.

For our students: Kindly complete this form in consultation with the head of the institution and/or the person-in-charge, department head or supervisor, the special project gatekeeper, depending on where you will conduct the project.

Student's name: Marielle O. Castro

Student number: 2020-30601

Batch of entry in UPOU: 2020

Email address: mocastro2@up.edu.ph

Contact number: 09566032792

Academic Term: 1st term 2nd term 3rd term AY: 2023-2024

Special Project Outcomes

After completing the course, the student should be able to:

1. Apply knowledge of educational research analyzing and evaluating an educational issue or problem; OR apply knowledge of instructional design in developing and testing an instructional program, resource, or technology;
2. Critically reflect on their experiences as they complete their special project; and
3. Demonstrate ethical practice and desirable professional work attitudes and skills

Special Project Requirements

Project Preliminary Report	the implementation sessions of the practicum plan with at least one: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Instructional Design Project: implementation or testing of instructional materials/resources, technology-supported education/training programs/curriculum/ modules/courses, or learning systems that the student developed which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/ external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199• Research Project: implementation of research project in an educational setting which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/ external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199
Class/Learner/ Program/ Needs Analysis	an analysis/ report based on observation of actual practice, interview of teacher/ department head/ program head, and or other pre-assessment or evaluation tools
Project Plan	a plan highlighting the specific activities and strategies that the student will implement to accomplish the assigned project task or work based on educational theories, concepts, and principles
Project Work	the implementation sessions of the project plan with at least one: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Instructional Design Project implementation or testing of instructional materials/resources, technology-supported education/training programs/curriculum/ modules/courses, or learning systems that the student developed which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/ external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199• Research Project: implementation of research project in an educational setting which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/

external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199

Project ePortfolio the collection of documents, reports, and relevant attachments showcasing learning from and analysis of the whole practicum experience, and providing evidence of achievement and accomplishments

Project eJournal a brief reflective journal on the insights gained, problems experienced and solutions made, and areas for improvement

Project presentation the presentation of the highlights of the special project which will be assessed by the FIC and monitored by the BES Program Chair

Student's signature: ms cartero Date: May 28, 2024

To the Head of Institution/ Practicum Supervisor,

I would like to express my deepest gratitude for extending your expertise and guidance to our student. With your help, our student will be able to achieve the objectives of the special project, gain invaluable knowledge and understanding of the work involved and required in the profession, as well as develops the skills needed in the field. Again, thank you very much.

Sincerely,

Asst. Prof. Leynard Gripal
Faculty-In-Charge, 2T 23-24 EDS 199 – Special Project

Gatekeeper/ External Adviser's Approval

Duties of the Gatekeeper:

- assigns tasks
- guides student in his/her accomplishment of tasks
- encourages creativity and innovation
- monitors progress
- provides regular feedback and comments
- signs practicum logs
- evaluates teaching demonstration/implementation or testing of output

This signifies my consent for the BES student to conduct special project in our institution/ organization/community class provided that s/he will abide by our policies and regulations. I understand that the student is expected to showcase creative and innovative application of theories and principles that s/he has learned from your undergraduate program in an actual professional work; thus, we shall provide the student with opportunities for such endeavor.

Name and Signature above Printed Name: CARMELA C. AGUSTIN

Designation: Social Welfare Officer II

Name of institution/ organization: TPNRC

Office number: _____ Email address: tpnrcbulacan@gmail.com

Date: May 28, 2024

APPENDIX C

Consent and Assent Form

CONSENT FORM

Name of researcher: Marielle O. Castro

Institution: University of the Philippines Open University

Research title: A Descriptive Study on the Modular Learning Experiences of Tanglaw Pag-asa Residents at the Senior High School Level

Part I: Information Sheet

The objective of this study is to explore the experiences of Tanglaw Pag-asa residents at the Senior High School level with modular learning. Modular Distance Learning is a learning modality where learners use Self-Learning Modules (SLMs), textbooks, worksheets, and other learning materials to gain an understanding of the subject matter. To achieve the study's objective, I will be conducting structured one-on-one interviews with respondents. It is an interview method where the researcher asks the respondents predetermined questions in the same order. In line with this, your participation is valuable to the success of this research project.

Research participants will be given the opportunity to share their thoughts on the effectiveness of modular learning and suggest ways to enhance their learning experiences in this learning setup. Note, however, that some of the questions the researcher will ask are somewhat personal and centered on participants' experiences. However, please be informed that participants may refuse to answer any of the questions. In such a case, the researcher will proceed immediately to the next question. It is also worth noting that the information I will collect for this research project will be treated with confidentiality and will not be used for other purposes.

If participants allow, interviews will be recorded for more efficient and systematic data collection and analysis. Please be reminded that participation in this study is voluntary and participants may withdraw whenever they deem fit. For those who agree to participate in the study, kindly fill out the certificate of consent below.

Part II: Certificate of Consent

- I have read and understood the above information and willingly agreed to take part in the study.
- I allow the researcher to use a recording device for the interviews.

Name and signature: _____

Date: _____

Signature of researcher: _____

ASSENT FORM

Name of researcher: Marielle O. Castro

Institution: University of the Philippines Open University

Research title: A Descriptive Study on the Modular Learning Experiences of Tanglaw Pag-asa Residents at the Senior High School Level

Part I: Information Sheet

The objective of this study is to explore the experiences of Tanglaw Pag-asa residents at the Senior High School level with modular learning. Modular Distance Learning is a learning modality where learners use Self-Learning Modules (SLMs), textbooks, worksheets, and other learning materials to gain an understanding of the subject matter. To achieve the study's objective, I will be conducting structured one-on-one interviews with respondents. It is an interview method where the researcher asks the respondents predetermined questions in the same order. In line with this, the participation of your child/ ward is valuable to the success of this research project.

Research participants will be given the opportunity to share their thoughts on the effectiveness of modular learning and suggest ways to enhance their learning experiences in this learning setup. Note, however, that some of the questions the researcher will ask are somewhat personal and centered on participants' experiences. However, please be informed that participants may refuse to answer any of the questions. In such a case, the researcher will proceed immediately to the next question. It is also worth noting that the information I will collect for this research project will be treated with confidentiality and will not be used for other purposes.

If participants allow, interviews will be recorded for more efficient and systematic data collection and analysis. Please be reminded that participation in this study is voluntary and participants may withdraw whenever they deem fit. For those who agree to participate in the study, kindly fill out the certificate of consent below.

Part II: Certificate of Consent

- I have read and understood the above information and consented to my child/ ward's participation in the study.
- I allow the researcher to use a recording device for the interviews.

Name of child/ward: _____

Name and signature: _____

Date: _____

Signature of researcher: _____

APPENDIX D

Interview guide

EDS 199 – SPECIAL PROJECT

Interview guide

Part I: Demographic information:

1. How old are you?	
2. Is your family income enough to meet your basic needs?	
3. Were you attending school before staying at Tanglaw Pag-asa? If yes, what did you like most and least about school? If not, what forced you to drop out of school?	
4. How long have you been staying at Tanglaw Pag-asa?	
5. What grade level are you in and what strand are you taking (HUMSS, ABM, STEM, GAS)?	

Part II: Main questions:

6. What is your day at Tanglaw Pag-asa like? What activities do you usually do?	
7. What learning style works best for you? <ul style="list-style-type: none">● <i>Visual- learning through images, diagrams, or charts</i>● <i>Auditory- learning by listening</i>● <i>Kinesthetic- learning by doing</i>● <i>Verbal- learning through written or spoken information</i>	
8. Can you describe your experiences with using Self-Learning Modules?	

For instance, how long do you usually read and answer modules? Do you submit them on time?	
9. What other learning resources do you use? For instance, library, textbooks, and activity sheets.	
10. What challenges do you often encounter? For instance, was there a particular topic you found difficult? Were there instances when you lacked motivation?	
11. What factors affect your motivation for learning? For instance, do you get motivated by rewards?	
12. Based on your experience, what are the strengths and weaknesses of modular learning?	
13. Is modular learning effective for individuals with visual/ auditory/ verbal/ kinesthetic) learning styles?	
14. What do you think can be done to enhance your learning experiences?	